

D6.4.1.1

Showcase description template

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Showcase description template

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General Information

Summary

The goal of this template is the documentation of showcases in NFDI4Energy. The following descriptions and definitions do not aim to be precise but rather intend to give a non-formal understanding of what showcases are, how they are different from use cases, why we need to document them, and what kind of information we need to document.

Use cases represent realistic energy system research projects with typical research questions, which integrate the application of a service, concept, or process from NFDI4Energy. When discussing or documenting **use cases**, they can be seen as a kind of a “planning device” before, throughout or even after the development of a service, concept, or process. It can relate to a small use case discussed when planning a certain service, or to the “large” use cases presented in the proposal, which integrate various concepts and services from NFDI4Energy. When discussing use cases before or throughout a project, we thus often envisage potential users and how these users will apply, for instance, a certain service for a certain purpose for a typical research question. A use case also can serve as educational material after development, for instance as part of a tutorial. While for a use case the application at first often is only anticipated, potential or theoretical, we use the term **showcase** if this application already has happened – some real person has used a NFDI4Energy service for some kind of real application. Accordingly, a use case can and at least theoretically at some point should lead to a showcase, but this might happen later in or outside of the work of the consortium.

The documentation of showcases has two purposes:

- 1) For the external presentation of the showcases on the [website](#).
- 2) As an internal documentation to be published as a deliverable on [Zenodo](#), for instance to provide feedback to services and record lessons learned.

Deliverable within NFDI4Energy

Task Area 6 “Use cases for community services” has the main objective to apply the services and concepts developed in NFDI4Energy to specific research examples. Besides the three main use cases included in the original funding proposal, throughout the work of the consortium showcases are identified, which are added as tasks with corresponding documentation deliverables in TA6 in the measure 6.4 “Showcases”.

Deliverable

The following page contains the template for documentation of the showcases. The template contains a longer segment to provide the documentation for internal use (as the basis for a more detailed description, for further discussions or as part of a deliverable), plus some points which will be used for presentation on the website only. All information which is used for the description on the website is marked in red. The three paragraphs for the website are based on the paragraphs from the longer documentation but should be briefer and oriented towards a wider audience.

When submitting the template, additionally potential visualization should be added, either own figures or links to stock photos. The following websites can be checked – the linked photos should be free to use.

Unsplash <https://unsplash.com/>

The Noun Project <https://thenounproject.com/photos>

Pexels <https://www.pexels.com>

Template

Internal Documentation

Title: Title of the showcase

Authors: Names and affiliations (this can be the authors of the original research, and/or the people associated with the showcase part of the research)

Contact person: Name and mailing address of the contact person

Date: Month when the showcase was finalized

Abstract: Short description of the showcase

Link: Relevant links, if possible

NFDI4Energy input: Which outcome of NFDI4Energy has been applied in this showcase? Here only briefly the names of services etc. should be given

TAs involved: Which task areas have been involved in the showcase?

Energy research: Here the actual energy system research should be described. What is the topic, the research question, the outcome? This part should be short but provide a good understanding of the scientific outcome of the research.

Enhancement: Here should be described, how outcomes of NFDI4Energy are applied. What has been done and what is the improvement?

Potential testimonials: If applicable, here potential sources or already existing comments to include on the website can be listed.

Lessons learned: Are there lessons from this showcase which can be used to improve, for instance, the service used, or are relevant more generally in the work of NFDI4Energy?

Brief sections for the website

The Showcase's Starting Point in Energy System Research

Here the actual energy research topic or question should be briefly described – this is the brief, website-friendly version of the “Energy Research” paragraph above.

Motivation and Research Requirements

This should describe the motivation for “doing something better” from a NFDI4Energy perspective, based on the “Meta Level” paragraph above.

NFDI4Energy Solution

Here it should be briefly described how NFDI4Energy services or concepts have been used, maybe success stories or testimonials can be added, etc. This corresponds to the “Enhancement” paragraph above.